

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	1
Work Package title	Project management and coordination of activities
Deliverable number	1.3.1.
Deliverable title	Steering Committee meeting report #1
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
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Deliverable due date	2019-08-31
Deliverable latest review date	2020-01-04
Comments	SC meeting was postponed from August (M08) to October 2019 (M10)

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1. Executive Summary

The first GUTTA Steering Committee (SC) meeting was originally planned for M08 of the project lifetime (i.e. August 2019), but was postponed to M10 for not interfering with the usual holidays season in both Italy and Croatia and with the reporting phase of the first reporting period (RP1).

The SC meeting consisted of two linked but separate events: a public event in the frame of EC-day 2019 and an internal meeting. The Project Partners (PP) had a preliminary ice-breaker city tour and dinner on the previous night. All events took place in Zagreb, Croatia, from October 1 to 2, 2019.

Scope of the EC-day event was to disseminate GUTTA project aims and the achieved results. Scope of the internal meeting was to review the status of implementation of the project, discuss criticalities, take decisions, and agree on future steps.

For the shortcuts employed in this report, we refer to the official GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1pEbyf1Rb7gAo8nyGAyfT_PyVqKrxFXkx

2. Tour of Zagreb old town and social dinner (October 1, 17:00-21:00)

Both the city tour and the social dinner are essential part of the first SC meeting, as they were meant for and contributed to the internal team building. They correspond to part 1 of the meeting.

Part	Time	
1	17:00	Guided tour of the old town of Zagreb Venue: Ban Jelačić Square (Zagreb, HR)
	19:00	Social Dinner Venue: Stari Fijaker, Mesnička ulica (Zagreb, HR)

Figure 1 Left: Itinerary of the walk tour in the old town of Zagreb. Starting point was the Ban Josip Jelačić Square. Right: some participants to the tour.

Table 1 List of participants to part 1 of the SC meeting.

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Davor	Deželjin	MMPI
2	Evangelia	Piteni	AdSP
3	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
4	Josip	Orović	UniZd
5	Maria	Mihalić	CSA
6	Martin	Zrilić	UniZd
7	Miguel	Madeira	EMSA
8	Mirna	Erlić	Unizd
9	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
10	Sandro	Vidas	CSA
11	Zoran	Pavin	UniZd

3. EC-day event (October 2, 8:30-11:00)

Participation to EC-day 2019 was planned already in the AF. The event is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, main outcomes, and online published contents.

2.1 Agenda

Part	Time	Venue:
		Ministry of Regional Development and EU Funds, Miramarska cesta 22, 10 000: Zagreb, Croatia
2	8:30 – 9:00	Registration
	9:00	Introduction and Chair (Sandro Vidas, CSA Mare Nostrum, Zagreb - Croatia)
	9:10	Greetings (Siniša Orlić, HR Ministry of Maritime Affairs, Transport and Infrastructure, Zagreb - Croatia)
	9:20	Publication of ships' CO2 emission data through the EMSA-Thetis platform (Miguel Madeira, EMSA, Lisbon- Portugal)
	9:35	The importance of Italy-Croatia Cross – Border Transport (Anija Vudrić, Coastal Shipping Agency, Split- Croatia)
	9:40	GUTTA project – Insights (Gianandrea Mannarini, CMCC, Lecce- Italy)
	9:55	Ferryboat vessel propulsion and performance data (Josip Orović, University of Zadar, Zadar - Croatia)
	10:10	New Maritime Routes for improving Italy-Croatia CB mobility (Evangelia Piteni, AdSP-MAM, Bari-Italy)
	10:25	Group Photo
	10:30	Coffee Break
	11:00	End of the event

2.2 Participants

The conference had 19 registered participants. The list of participants is given in

Table 2. CSA archives the original signed registration sheets.

Table 2 List of participants to the EC-day 2019 event of the GUTTA project (part2 of the SC meeting).

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Anija	Vudrić	Coastal Shipping Agency
2	Damir	Lakoš	Trinity House London licensed North Sea Pilot
3	Davor	Deželjin	MMPI
4	Evangelia	Piteni	AdSP
5	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
6	Josip	Orović	UniZd
7	Ksenija	Štambuk Zajec	Ministry of Regional Development and fund of EU - Islands Commission
8	Lovre	Ševerdija	Rapska plovidba
9	Maria	Mihalić	CSA
10	Martin	Zrilić	UniZd
11	Miguel	Madeira	EMSA
12	Mirna	Erlić	Unizd
13	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
14	Sandro	Vidas	CSA
15	Sanja	Rendić-Miočević	Ministry of Regional Development and fund of EU - Islands Commission
16	Sanjin	Kuljanić	Jadrolinija
17	Siniša	Orlić	MMPI
18	Zlatko	Košta	MMPI
19	Zoran	Pavin	UniZd

Figure 2 An initial moment of the EC-day event.

2.3 Main outcomes

The conference ran on schedule. It was moderated by Maria Mihalić from CSA. A few questions arose during the presentations and plenty of opportunity was there for informal exchange and networking during the subsequent 30-min coffee break. The key messages by each speaker are summarized in the following paragraphs:

Vidas

He greeted all participants and invited captain Sinisa Orlić, Assistant Minister of the Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure, Navigation Safety Directorate, to open the conference.

Orlić

He underlined the fact that there are 70 Mton dangerous goods transported every year in the Adriatic Sea. Furthermore, the Ministry is committed to protection of sea, air quality, and climate. Thus, the Ministry welcomes both EU MRV and the GUTTA project as contributions to the achievement of this mission.

Madeira

He presented the main features of the website <https://mrv.emsa.europa.eu/#public/emission-report> through which EMSA since July 1, 2019 has distributed the MRV data. They consist in both an interactive datagrid and csv file:

- The datagrid is a real-time repository of information (it is immediately and automatically published after each ship company's data submission).
- The csv file instead is published at most once a day, overnight and automatically, and just if a change of the records is detected by the system.

Then Mr. Madeira stated that, in both v2 and v3 of the csv file, 3 ships were entered by the ship companies with wrong scale for the CO₂ emissions, resulting in values 1000 times larger than actually monitored. He provided some other information about temporal variations of the contents of the MRV dataset along the past 3 months, highlighting that the total CO₂ emissions was rather stable and modifications were quite localized to a few Ships/Verifiers.

Finally, he reported that, as of Sept.23, 2019, the MRV dataset consisted of:

- 16 870 ships
- 11 653 emission reports
- 11 589 DoCs (Documents of Compliance)
- 5 568 monitoring plans (i.e., submitted by the Company on a voluntary basis; of which only 10% assessed by the Verifier)

Vudrić

She reviewed the main features of all existing CB routes between Italy and Croatia, including both vessels below and above 5 000 GT (i.e. the threshold for EU MRV). She then said that, when a ship operators proposes a new route, this has to be checked by both the involved Port Authorities and the Harbour Masters. The Coastal Shipping Agency (AZOLLP) only provides a final approval of the proposed route.

Mannarini

He presented the aims and implementation status of GUTTA project, recalling the Climate Change mitigation challenge to which the project is supposed to contribute. The main project achievements so far are:

- a partial recodification in python language of the existing VISIR ship routing model for adding new functionalities (validation vs. VISIR version in matlab is ongoing)
- a preliminary investigation of some statistical properties of the MRV dataset, in particular data related to RoPax vessels (a software for automated analysis has been developed by CMCC).

Orović

He reported about both some cruises performed by UniZd for collecting ferryboat CO2 emission data and he updated about advancements based on the ship simulator recently acquired by UniZd:

- Concerning the cruises, one regarded MV “Marko Polo” (in May 2019) and the other one MV “Zadar” (in September 2019). Data were collected by means of the “Testo 350” analyzer. They included both CO2 and a few air quality parameters. In conjunction with the measurements, some bridge parameters were also recorded, such speed and course of the ferryboat, its engine power and fuel consumption, and the rpm. Furthermore, environmental data regarding qualitative observations of wind and wave were recorded.
- Concerning the simulator, the engine room simulator (“Wärtsilä ERS 5000 TechSim simulator model MAN Diesel 32/40 Twin Medium Speed Engine + CPP - RoPax Ferry”) acquired through GUTTA project funds was integrated with the bridge simulator (“NTPro 5000 Navigation Simulator”) acquired using funds from other projects. The joint operation of afore mentioned models is, as of now, fully operational and it can simulate the seakeeping and propulsion characteristics of a ferry of 125 m in length and service speed of about 19 knots.

Piteni

She described the situation of AdSP ports and their perspectives. Some crucial interests of AdSP include: integration with the rail connection and reduction of road congestion and development of the retroports. A relevant policy tool could be the Special Economic Zones (Z.E.S.) foreseen by the Italian legislation.

The Bari port is equipped with both a PMIS (Port Management Information System) managed by the Italian Coast Guard and a PCS (Port Community System, called “Gaia”). Furthermore the feasibility of a LNG storage facility at Bari harbour was discussed in the frame of SUPER-LNG project¹.

Traffic data at the harbours controlled by the AdSP-MAM are available online:

<https://www.adspmam.it/i-porti/statistiche/> and might be used for contributing to deliverable D.3.1.2

Finally, Mrs. Piteni proposes Barletta as the Italian harbour for the new CB route to be facilitated by the GUTTA project. At Barletta harbour seabed depth is close to 7 m², thus being suited for vessels with draught up to 5 m (like most RoPax already operating between Italy and Croatia).

¹ <https://superlng.adrioninterreg.eu/>

² https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Porto_di_Barletta#Caratteristiche

2.4 Online resources

Evidence of the EC-day event was published on the portal of the EC-day initiative:

<https://www.ecday.eu/event/steering-committee-conference-project-gutta/>

Furthermore, a few press releases can be found online:

- Morsky.hr: <http://bit.ly/35rncX>
- UniZd.hr: <http://bit.ly/35o97BC>
- UniZd Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/unizd/posts/1466333893519280>
- Pomorac.hr: <http://pomorac.net/2019/10/08/hub-mare-nostrum-organizirala-dan-europske-suradnje-u-sklopu-projekta/>

Figura 3 Screenshot of the EC-day page relative to the GUTTA event of Oct.2, 2019.

4. Internal meeting (October 2, 11:00- 17:00)

The second part of the SC meeting consisted in a PP-internal meeting , that is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, and main outcomes.

4.1 Agenda

Part	Time	Venue:
		Ministry of Regional Development and EU Funds, Miramarska cesta 22, 10 000: Zagreb, Croatia
3	11:00	General overview of project implementation status (Paola Agostini, CMCC)
	11:30	CSA implementation status (Sandro Vidas, CSA)
	11:45	UniZd implementation status (Josip Orović, UniZd)
	12:00	MMPI implementation status (Davor Deželjin, MMPI)
	12:15	AdSP implementation status (Lia Piteni, AdSP)
	12:30	Lunch served in the Ministry's hall
4	13:30	Thematic Work Packages issues (Gianandrea Mannarini, CMCC)
	14:00	Discussion (all PP)
	15:15	Coffee Break
	15:30	Management and communication issues (Paola Agostini, CMCC)
	16:00	Discussion (all PP)
	17:00	SC meeting closure

4.2 Participants

The complete list of participants is given in Table 3. They are the same for part 3 and part 4 of the meeting. CSA archives the originally signed registration sheets.

Table 3 List of participants to the internal part of the event (parts 3 and 4 of the SC meeting). Mr. Davor Dezeljin, MMPI could not attend part 4 for personal reasons.

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Davor	Deželjin	MMPI
2	Evangelia	Piteni	AdSP
3	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
4	Josip	Orović	UniZd
5	Maria	Mihalić	CSA
6	Martin	Zrilić	UniZd
7	Miguel	Madeira	EMSA
8	Mirna	Erlić	Unizd

9	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
10	Sandro	Vidas	CSA
11	Zoran	Pavin	UniZd

4.3 Main outcomes

4.3.1 – Part 3 of the meeting

Agostini

She reported about the technical and financial implementation status after RP1. Overall, GUTTA is lagging behind by about 30% both in terms of implementation of the activities and financial absorption. There is a need during RP2 to engage for recovering the cumulated gap and implement the many deliverables expected by end of the present reporting period.

Vidas

He mentioned as a main result achieved by CSA that Jadrolinija is now interested in evaluating optimization of their ferry routes based on the expected outcomes of GUTTA.

Also, he made following points:

- CSA worked with Malta on a proposal for a review of the MRV parameters;
- The 2022 ballast waters convention was already ratified by Croatia, not yet by Italy;

Orović

He states that GUTTA activities by UniZd proceeds as planned. A draft report for D.3.1.3 is ready and will be distributed soon.

Deželjin

MMPI is placing GUTTA project posters at MMPI premises and on its institutional website. Photos of the posters and URL of the website will be provided.

Concerning extraction of AIS data, it could be easier to get them from the SEG database of EMSA than from MMPI: <http://emsa.europa.eu/seg-user-training/seg-get-started-guide/download/5258/2995/23.html>

Pitenti

She informed that, at the moment, AdSP still needs to open the call for recruiting the FLC for GUTTA. Furthermore, she gave availability for hosting GUTTA SC meeting #2 in Bari on April 1-2, 2020.

D.3.1.2 “Report on CB maritime traffic data” (in charge: MMPI, due: M09)

Due to its relevance for the SO3 of GUTTA, the internal discussion relative to this deliverable is reported in the following.

Concerning the new CB route, an hypothesis could be to have a ferry operating on the round trip: Zadar-Dubrovnik-Bari/Barletta-Zadar. This way, Zadar and Dubrovnik would be linked avoiding Bosnia's bottleneck (in fact the planned Peljesac bridge will need two more years, besides some extra time for realizing the related road infrastructures).

Pitoni added that even a detour via Igoumenitsa (Greece) could make sense (see Fig.4). Igoumenitsa Port Authority representatives could be invited to a GUTTA stakeholder's meeting for discussing this. Traffic data at the harbours controlled by the AdSP-MAM are available online: <https://www.adspmam.it/i-porti/statistiche/> and might be used for preparing this deliverable³.

Figure 4: Hypothesis of a new CB round trip route involving both Italy, Croatia, and Greece. Blue legs: existing routes; Red legs: new route.

³ Difference between “analisi congiunturale” and “analisi tendenziale”:

http://guide.supereva.it/economia_politica/interventi/2009/11/variazioni-tendenziali-e-variazioni-congiunturali

4.3.2 – Part 4 of the meeting

This session was split into two subparts:

4.3.2.1 *Thematic Work Packages issues*

This subsession focused on implementation status and plans for selected project Deliverables due in RP2, RP3, and RP4.

4.3.2.2 *Management and communication issues*

This subsession focused on WP1 and WP2 activities and issues.

4.4 Online resources

The presentations of parts 2-4 were shared at the URL:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1doxJhfaYL_tOTNiDbucZcL1YcBg2T87x

Conclusions

The GUTTA SC meeting #1 was a quite productive event with a full participation from project partners, advisory board, and also a few external stakeholders.

From this meeting a recommendation emerges, to have a stakeholder meeting at latest in conjunction with next GUTTA SC meeting (April 2020) in order to discuss following two key points:

- Subscription of a MoU between Italian and Croatian ferry operators for sharing CO2 emission data for research purposes (cf. GUTTA SO 1,2);
- Involvement of Igoumenitsa Port Authority in a discussion about the new CB route, which could be designed in a way to serve also this Greek port cf. GUTTA SO 3).